

TRADITIONAL METHOD OF NEM SEED OIL EXTRACTION IN NORTH EASTERN NIGERIA: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS.

*Oluwole, F. A; Oumaru, M. B.; and Abdulrahim, A. T.

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

A study was carried out on the traditional method of processing neem seed oil. Six major operations are involved in the production process namely: collection of seeds, cleaning/sorting of seeds, shelling/winnowing of seeds to separate the kernel from the shell, hulling/winnowing to separate the seed from the shell, crushing of kernel (size reduction) using mortar and pestle and extraction of oil. All the operations are currently carried out manually. The problems associated with this processing method were identified to include inefficient (as it only extracts about 35.26 % of available oil), tedious and time consuming. Solutions that will improve the quality and quantity of the product were proposed.

KEYWORDS: Neem seed, kernel, kneading, extraction. Mortar, pestle, oil

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Corresponding Author: engrfasiu@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Neem tree is a member of mahogany family, meliaceae today known by the botanic name *Azadiradita Indica* meaning “tree of India” and commonly known in major Nigerian languages of Hausa and Yoruba, as maina and dogonyaro tree respectively. The neem tree is a fast growing and long living tree, native to Burma in India, to tropical south East Asia and now growing all over the world for it can survive droughts and poor soil and keep its leaves all year round (Puri, 1999, OIA and PGA, 1992). It is a tall tree, up to 30 meter high, with leafy spreading branches. Many white flowers which smell of honey appear for the first time when the neem is 2 to 3 years old, and the tree bear fruit after 3 to 5 years. The ripe fruit are about 2 cm long and oval shaped. Inside the fruit there is oil and the extract is very strong, bitter with garlic/sulfuric or pungent smell.

Neem trees can be grown in areas, which have between 400mm and 1500mm of rainfall each year. It performs best at an altitude of less than 1500 meters. Neem trees will survive very hot temperature up to 44 °C and as low as 4 °C. Neem tree have many beneficial uses for natural insecticide, cosmetics ingredient, health treatment, soap and toothpaste ingredient, cure for malaria etc (Puri, 1999, OIA and PGA, 1992). The most commonly used part of neem tree is the seed. Neem seed has oil content of about 40-58.9% by weight (Puri, 1999, OIA and PGA, 1992). The extracted oil is used as insecticide for it provides protection not only against mosquitoes but from insects bite. It is also used in treating skin diseases such as eczema, skin allergies, as shampoo for controlling scalp, dandruff, as moisturizing oil. It is also used in agriculture to control plant pests and diseases. It is used as lubricant. Even though the neem tree has many potential applications; the utilization of this tree in Nigeria for industrial purposes is not yet exploited, as it is only used to treat malaria and as canopy tree.

The refined and purified neem oil has the following characteristics: specific gravity 0.9087; refractive index 1.4612; iodine value (Wij's) 66.4; saponification value 290.9; and unsaponifiable matter 0.8% (Felycia *et al.*, 2008). Extraction of oil from neem seeds can be performed using three different methods: mechanical extraction, solvent extraction, and supercritical fluid extraction. Mechanical extraction is the common method used to extract the neem

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oil from the seed (Fasina and Ajibola, 1989), since this method is effective for seed containing 30-70% oil (Ketaren *et al.*, 1986). The mechanical extraction has several advantages compared to the other methods, such as simple equipment and low investment, low operating cost, and the oil does not undergo solvent separation process, etc. (Fasina and Ajibola, 1989).

Effect of extraction condition on quality of oil has been investigated by a number of researchers, including conophor nut (Fasina and Ajibola, 1989), groundnut (Adeeko and Ajibola, 1990), peanut kernel oil (Damame *et al.*, 1990), virgin olive oil (Torres and Maestri, 2006) and castor oil (Oluwole *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 1: Neem trees

Traditional Method of Neem Seed Oil Extraction

The traditional method of neem seed oil extraction presently practice in the north eastern Nigeria permits the extraction of about 17.63% from the kernel, which is inefficient and time consuming. The traditional method of neem seed oil involves the following steps:

- i. Collection of fruits/seeds.
Fruits and dry seeds are collected from neem trees.
- ii. Cleaning, drying and sorting of seeds.
The ripe fruits and seeds collected are cleaned by washing in ordinary water and rubbing with the palms to remove the skin of the fruits. The cleaned seeds are then dried by spreading in the sun to reduce the moisture content of the seeds. This is followed by removing unwanted materials such as stones and dirt by hand picking (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Dried Neem seeds in a container

- iii. Shelling of seed and winnowing.
Shelling of seeds to obtain clean kernel is carried out by the use of grinding stones as shown Figure 3 and winnowing is achieved by holding baskets filled with mixture of seeds and shells at arm length and gradually emptying them. If there is strong wind, the pieces of shell will be blown away, if not, the operation is repeated many times as described by Fleury (1985) and Papu *et al.*, (2009). Figure 3 shows the shelling method used in the study area and Figure 4 shows the shelled neem seeds.

Figure 3: Shelling of neem seed using grinding stone

Figure 4: Shelled neem seeds

- v. Crushing of kernel.
Crushing of kernel to reduce size is normally done by women using grinding stones or pounding mortar and pestle as shown in Figure 5 (a and b) respectively.

Figure 5: Crushing of kernels

(a) Crushing with stone

(b) Crushing with mortar and pestle

- vi. Sieving of ground neem seed to obtain fine particles.
Sieving is carried out using the traditional sieve as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Sieving to get fine particles

- vii. Extraction of oil:
Oil extraction is carried out by stirring the fine particles with wooden stick in a bowl and gradually adding hot water (90 °C) to form dough as shown in Figure 7 (a and b).

Figure 7: Stirring to form dough

- viii. Kneading and pressing to extract oil.
After the formation of dough, it is pressed with hand on a grinding stone until oil starts gushing out as shown in Figure 8. The oil is then scooped off into an empty dried container.

Figure 8: kneading to form dough and pressing out the oil

Wiemer and Korthals (1989) and Oluwole *et al.*, (2012) reported that drying of oil could be achieved by heating to 130 °C to remove all traces of moisture. The adopted method in the study area is by heating until there is no more cracking sound of water molecules this is done by experience. Figure 9 shows the collected dried neem seed oil.

Figure 9: Extracted neem seed oil

As could be observed, all the operations mentioned above are currently carried out manually. Table 1 shows the results obtained from the traditional extraction of neem seed oil in the study area. From Table 2 it is observed that about 17.63% oil was obtained, which is about 35.26% of the oil present in the kernel. This shows that the traditional method of neem seed oil extraction is inefficient, tedious and time-consuming.

Table 1: Results of Neem Seed Oil obtained from three processors

S/No.	Mass of neem seed M_1 (kg)	Mass of oil M_2 (kg)	Oil Yield $(M_2/M_1) \times 100$ %	*Oil Recovery $((M_2/XM_1) \times 100$ %
1	9.10	1.41	15.49	30.98
2	12.10	1.91	15.79	31.58
3	11.63	1.68	14.45	28.90
4	13.62	2.80	20.56	41.12
5	15.21	3.07	20.18	40.36
Sum	61.66	10.87	20.18	40.36
Av.	12.33±2.046	2.17 ± 0.647	17.63	35.26

*X = oil content of neem seed

PROBLEMS AND CONSTRAINTS OF NEEM SEED OIL PROCESSING IN NORTH-EASTERN NIGERIA

There are several problems and constraints confronting or limiting the processing of neem seed oil in terms of quantity, quality and profitability in this region. Some of these problems are as follows:

- a. problems associated with the unit operations involved in the processing procedures.
 - i. lack of plantation of neem seed.
Neem seeds are collected by searching under the scattered trees. Individual control over scattered trees are not possible, this invariably affects the quantity of neem seeds obtain per individual processor.

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- ii. lack of processing equipment.
As could be observed, all the unit operations involved in the processing of neem seed are currently carried out manually. These unit operations are laborious and time consuming, most especially crushing of the kernel with mortar and pestle which could not give fine particles for efficient fat extraction (Oluwole *et al.*, 2012). As a result, the present status of neem seed processing remains the extraction of its oil, which is performed by women and children, using traditional methods of extraction.
- iii. lack of commercial processing plants
Lack of commercial processing plants is not encouraging people to go into neem seed business.
- b. problems associated with government policies
 - i. lack of government promotional programmes
There is no promotional program for neem seed production like other crops such as cassava, rice, groundnut, sesame seeds etc.
 - ii. Lack of control body for neem seed products
There is no regulatory body to oversee the activities of the neem seed processors for example neem seed farmers association and neem seed market board like the cocoa board, groundnut board etc.
 - iii. Unavailability of standard or organized market for neem seed products

THE WAY FORWARD

For these problems to be solved, the three tiers of government have a lot to do.

- i. Government and private sectors should create an awareness of the importance of neem seed products.
- ii. Government and private sectors should invest on and encourage the fabrication of processing equipment through appropriate technology initiatives.
- iii. Research and development effort is therefore necessary towards an appropriate technology for the processing of neem seed oil to provide the needed solutions to problems facing the local processors of the oil in this part of Nigeria.

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